

Semantic Communications with RIC-Centric AI-Driven Orchestration for 6G Networks

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Abstract—Semantic and goal-oriented communications are emerging as a key paradigm for future 6G networks. However, many existing approaches focus on semantic models and algorithms in isolation, often overlooking the architectural, operational, and time-scale constraints of real network deployments. In this paper, we address this gap by presenting a RIC-centric framework for semantic communications grounded in the O-RAN architecture, enabling the coordinated realization of semantic intelligence across heterogeneous control layers and time scales. Building on a unified semantic management framework spanning the Non-Real-Time and Near-Real-Time RIC, we show how semantic objectives, AI-based orchestration, and adaptive L1/L2 control can be jointly integrated while accounting for energy efficiency, computation costs, and deployment realism. The framework is evaluated through three representative case studies covering semantic-aware MAC operation for IoT data collection, collaborative edge intelligence with goal-aware inference, and AI-driven RAN control over a commercial-grade O-RAN-compliant network. The results demonstrate how semantic communications can be effectively instantiated across different layers and time scales, providing actionable insights toward deployable, AI-native 6G systems.

Index Terms—Semantic communications, 6G networks, O-RAN, RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), AI-based orchestration, adaptive L1/L2 control, edge intelligence, sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Semantic and goal-oriented communications are increasingly regarded as a key paradigm for future 6G networks, enabling a shift from bit-level reliability toward the efficient delivery of information that is relevant for a given task, goal, or application outcome [1]. By leveraging advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), semantic communications promise improvements in communication efficiency, scalability, and resource utilization, especially in data-intensive scenarios such as Internet of Things (IoT) sensing and edge intelligence [2], [3].

A first line of research has investigated semantic communications at the protocol and access layers, proposing mechanisms that explicitly exploit information relevance to reduce communication overhead and energy consumption. Representative approaches include content-based wake-up

Fig. 1. Semantic-aware O-RAN architecture.

and semantic-driven data sourcing for IoT systems [4], [5], freshness-aware and Value-of-Information (VoI)-driven access schemes, and semantic-query-activated random access for correlated traffic [6]. These works demonstrate that semantic awareness can significantly improve efficiency at the device and Medium Access Control (MAC) levels, particularly in large-scale and energy-constrained deployments.

In parallel, semantic-aware collaborative inference and distributed intelligence at the network edge have been widely studied. Several contributions have explored communication-efficient collaboration based on feature sharing, task relevance, and semantic abstraction, showing that inference accuracy can be improved while limiting communication costs [7]–[9]. More recent studies have highlighted the importance of jointly accounting for semantic relevance and wireless channel conditions when forming collaborative groups, especially in realistic wireless environments [10], [11].

Despite these advances, most existing works still consider semantic communication mechanisms largely in isolation from the underlying network control architecture. In practice, semantic processing interacts with system-level constraints

such as latency requirements, control-plane overhead, energy footprint, and deployment realism. This gap has motivated increasing interest in architecture-aware solutions and AI-driven control frameworks, particularly within open and disaggregated Radio Access Network (RAN) architectures such as Open RAN (O-RAN) [12], where hierarchical control and policy-based orchestration are enabled through RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs).

However, the explicit integration of semantic communications into a RIC-centric control plane—covering the placement of semantic functions, the coordination between Non-Real-Time (Non-RT) and Near-Real-Time (Near-RT) control loops, and the interaction with adaptive Layer 1 (L1) and Layer 2 (L2) mechanisms—remains insufficiently explored. Moreover, sustainability aspects, including the energy cost of semantic processing and AI model execution, are often only implicitly considered, despite their relevance for scalable and realistic deployments [3], [13].

This paper addresses these gaps by presenting a RIC-centric framework for semantic communications grounded in the O-RAN architecture. The proposed approach enables the coordinated realization of semantic intelligence across heterogeneous control layers and time scales, while explicitly accounting for architectural constraints, deployment realism, and energy-related considerations. Part of the presented framework and results builds upon the outcomes of the SNS JU project 6G-GOALS [14], [15], which are here consolidated and extended within a unified system-level perspective.

The framework is illustrated and validated through three representative case studies, covering semantic-aware MAC operation for IoT data collection, collaborative edge intelligence with goal- and wireless-aware grouping, and AI-driven RAN control implemented over a commercial-grade O-RAN-compliant network. Key challenges are addressed by improving radio resource efficiency, reducing irrelevant data traffic and network overhead, and enhancing inference accuracy through Near- and Non-RT adaptation of resource sharing for heterogeneous traffic, and device collaboration policies. Sustainability considerations are also taken into account, by adopting a holistic view of the system energy footprint, enabling energy-aware decisions across different control layers, while acknowledging the costs associated with semantic processing and AI model execution. Overall, the results highlight the importance of architecture-aware semantic design and provide practical insights toward deployable AI-native 6G systems.

II. RIC-CENTRIC ARCHITECTURE FOR SEMANTIC COMMUNICATIONS

Semantic communications in future 6G systems aim to transcend traditional bit-level reliability by enabling the exchange of meaning, intent, and task-relevant information. Realising this vision requires a fundamental shift in the design of the control plane, from traffic-oriented optimisation to semantics-aware orchestration. Within this context, the O-RAN architec-

ture, centered on the RICs, provides a flexible and AI-native framework for enabling a semantic control plane.

The RIC architecture comprises two key components: the Non-RT RIC, operating within the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) layer, and the Near-RT RIC, deployed closer to the RAN edge. The Non-RT RIC is responsible for high-level reasoning, global optimization, and policy enforcement over time scales exceeding one second. It orchestrates AI/ML models and distributes semantic policies through the A1 interface to the Near-RT RIC, which executes time-critical control and dynamic RAN reconfiguration within a 10 ms to 1 s latency range. These functionalities are exposed via standardized interfaces such as A1, R1, and E2, enabling cross-layer coordination and modular software integration.

Semantic control in this architecture, as shown in Fig. 1, can be realized through the deployment of semantic-enabled RICs, referred to as Semantic RICs (S-RICs), which extend the traditional roles of rApps and xApps. These software modules are enhanced with capabilities to infer user intent, extract contextual knowledge, and dynamically adjust RAN behavior based on semantic relevance. For instance, semantic information flows such as knowledge graphs or user intents may be monitored and exploited to optimize scheduling, prioritize mission-critical data, or suppress redundant transmissions. The S-RICs coordinate the execution of AI/ML pipelines, manage the lifecycle of semantic inference models, and translate service goals into low-level control actions across the RIC hierarchy.

Integrating semantics into the control architecture introduces several challenges. One core issue lies in the representation and dissemination of semantic goals using existing interfaces, particularly in translating high-level intent into actionable policies for xApps via the A1 interface, or for RAN nodes via E2 service models. Another difficulty concerns the coordination between semantic inference and RAN functionalities. A critical limitation is the insufficient support for end-to-end interactions involving User Equipment (UE) and applications, as there are no defined mechanisms to collect contextual insights or semantic requirements from devices. Furthermore, semantic communication relies on shared understanding, necessitating standardized formats for knowledge representation, such as ontologies or knowledge graphs, to ensure interoperability across network entities.

To address these gaps, the architecture introduces specific elements within the UE and the edge or cloud platform: a Semantic Module for context processing, interpretation and compression, and a Semantic Extractor embedded in the application layer extracting high-level representations and selecting only essential semantic elements for transmission. Crucially, the Y1 interface must evolve from a one-way analytics channel into a bidirectional interface capable of transporting semantic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and policy feedback, enabling the Near-RT RIC to receive semantic requirements and enforce optimized policies.

In summary, the RIC-centric architecture for semantic communications enables a transformative shift in how networks

understand and respond to application needs. By embedding semantics into the control loop, it supports goal-oriented resource allocation, adaptive service negotiation, and context-aware RAN slicing, laying the foundation for the intelligent and intent-driven networks envisioned for 6G.

III. AI-BASED SEMANTIC MANAGEMENT, ORCHESTRATION, AND ADAPTIVE L1/L2 CONTROL

Semantic communications inherently require coordinated decisions ranging from long-term AI-driven orchestration to fast, time-critical adaptations at the PHYSical (PHY) and MAC layers. Building on the RIC-centric architecture for semantic communications introduced in Section II, this section focuses on the operational realization of semantic intelligence across the RAN. While the previous section addressed the architectural placement of semantic functions, the emphasis here is on how semantic management, orchestration, and control are executed over time, accounting for heterogeneous time scales and system constraints. To this end, we introduce a hierarchical semantic management framework spanning the Non-RT and Near-RT RIC, which enables closed-loop operation from high-level semantic objectives down to adaptive L1/L2 control actions. Specifically, Section III-A presents the semantic management loop for RAN operations, Section III-B focuses on AI-based semantic orchestration and holistic energy/computation control at the Non-RT layer, and Section III-C details adaptive L1/L2 control mechanisms for semantic communications at the Near-RT layer.

A. Semantic Management Loop for RAN Operations

We propose a set of semantic management loops to enable automated semantic operations in the RAN, as shown in Fig. 2. The loops cover orchestration, semantic AI model lifecycle management, knowledge management, and energy control, forming a continuous observation–decision–actuation pipeline across multiple timescales. In particular, fast-time-scale adaptations are handled by the Near-RT RIC, whereas long-horizon optimization and governance are performed by the Non-RT RIC/SMO.

1) *Semantic-aware RAN orchestration and adaptive L1/L2 control*: This loop is driven by semantic-relevant observability from the RAN, including UE-, application-, and network-level KPIs and contextual information, primarily collected via the E2 interface. When needed, aggregated views and longer-term statistics are obtained via O1 and the SMO. Building on our previous work [1], the proposed S-RIC extends conventional RIC functions by incorporating semantic context, task intent, and service objectives into radio control. Based on the observed network states and orchestration policies, the S-RIC updates its control applications (e.g., rApps/xApps/dApps), orchestrates radio resources, and performs *adaptive L1/L2 control* to preserve semantic task success while maintaining spectrum and energy efficiency under varying conditions.

2) *SemComOps: Semantic AI model lifecycle loop*: Semantic communication deploys in-network semantic encoders/decoders and inference components, following an

Fig. 2. Semantic management loops for RAN control.

AI/ML-driven design paradigm. Semantic communication operations (SemComOps) therefore manage their lifecycle, training, deployment, monitoring, and updating, using semantic-centric KPIs (e.g., intent satisfaction, semantic fidelity, and goal achievement) rather than solely bit-level metrics. Receiver-side feedback and environmental dynamics (e.g., traffic variations, context changes, or model drift) trigger model selection, fine-tuning, or retraining, coordinated across RIC timescales to keep semantic models robust and aligned with service objectives.

3) *Knowledge base management loop*: Knowledge alignment is fundamental to semantic encoding, interpretation, and control. This loop maintains domain- and context-specific knowledge to ensure consistent semantic behavior across users, cells, and network entities. We adopt a hierarchical and distributed knowledge base architecture that integrates heterogeneous information, including user-side semantic feedback, intra-RAN context, and cross-RAN spatio-temporal knowledge. This enables scalable knowledge sharing and timely alignment, supporting semantic-aware decisions across the management loops.

4) *Energy-aware semantic control loop*: Semantic processing and AI inference incur non-negligible energy costs; thus, energy efficiency must be managed jointly with semantic performance. This loop monitors energy consumption and enforces energy objectives or Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) across entities and timescales, selecting actions from local optimizations to network-level coordination. In a RIC-centric realization, energy-saving actions (e.g., resource throttling or operating-mode adaptation) are applied only when semantic KPIs remain within target bounds, enabling a controlled trade-off between semantic effectiveness and sustainability.

B. AI-Based Semantic Orchestration and Holistic Energy/Computation Control (Non-RT)

Designing an AI based Semantic Orchestration and energy-oriented closed-loop control for semantic communication as

introduced in the previous paragraph requires four capabilities: (i) measurement or estimation of energy consumption at each semantic communication module (semantic encoding and compression); (ii) estimation of energy consumption at the RF-transmission level; (iii) integration of collected or estimated energy metrics as feedback to prediction models and decision-making modules; and (iv) optimization mechanisms to adjust semantic encoding parameters that affect energy consumption.

The semantic control plane of the reference architecture in Fig. 1 provides the signaling and data-exchange mechanisms necessary to update semantic module parameters and thereby regulate UE level energy consumption from both local inference processing and air-interface transmissions. Regulation can be expressed by a communication Quality-of-Service (QoS) constraint tied to the communication goal (e.g., full image/text transfer, semantic segmentation or classification, or transmission of embeddings for downstream use). Objectives include prolonging the lifetime of the UE battery, managing recharging opportunities, or enforcing per-application energy quota in systems where compute and radio resources are shared.

At the application layer, a typical closed-loop action is the selection among semantic encoder models and model variants pruned at different levels. Pruning model trades off QoS (inherited from pruned-model performance), encoder inference energy, and latency. For example, a semantic encoder model based on deep learning can be pruned at various percentages and across different architecture levels producing a range of accuracies and multiply-accumulate operations. Each pruned model can then be further optimized for a target device—e.g., graphics processing units and neural processing units—and for different inference batch sizes, all of which affect energy and latency.

Offering such panel of pre-trained and optimized encoders, an energy-regulation process can be considered as selecting parameter combinations (including processing-unit frequency or power draw limit, pruned-model multiply-accumulate operations, batch size) in near-real time, subject to AI-device dynamics, radio-link conditions, and the latency to deliver parameter recommendations from the radio controller to the process controlling the encoder settings via the semantic plane (see Fig. 2). Recommendations may be required within tight near-time deadlines, considering targeted communication goal QoS, encoding latency, and available radio bandwidth at the time.

Given the combinatorial parameter space and these constraints, Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a natural candidate when learning is performed across representative observations and constraints, and the action space covers feasible parameter-value combinations for deployment. During the RL model learning phase, observations can be considered as both inference and radio transmission energy consumption values produced by pretrained energy-prediction models. A considered reward function is a distance between the predicted consumed energy and an energy regulation target, weighted by deviations of achieved communication goal QoS and latency

and by the mismatch between encoder-generated throughput and computed available radio bandwidth at the time.

C. Adaptive L1/L2 Control for Semantic Communications (Near-RT)

To fully unlock the potential of semantic communication in O-RAN, both L1 and L2 must be fundamentally redesigned to incorporate semantic awareness in a tightly integrated, context-aware, and computationally efficient manner. Traditional systems treat all transmitted bits uniformly, without regard to their underlying meaning,¹ focusing instead on reliable and efficient delivery through mechanisms such as Hybrid Automatic Repeat reQuest (HARQ), beamforming, and Adaptive Modulation and Coding (AMC). Semantic communication challenges this assumption by introducing unequal information value: some bits encode essential semantic content and are therefore significantly more important than others. This shift calls for semantics-aware L1 physical-layer mechanisms capable of prioritizing the protection and retransmission of critical data, while allowing controlled degradation or loss of less meaningful information. As a consequence, L1 reliability metrics must be redefined. Rather than relying exclusively on Bit Error Rate (BER) or Block Error Rate (BLER), the system should incorporate semantic performance measures that reflect how effectively the received data preserve the intended meaning. Achieving this will require new modulation and coding strategies that adapt not only to channel conditions but also to semantic importance. For instance, deep learning-based encoders could assign highly robust codewords to high-value semantic units, while mapping lower-importance information to higher-throughput yet less reliable configurations. Whereas traditional resource allocation follows predefined QoS profiles, semantic-aware communication demands real-time adjustment of transmission parameters—such as power allocation, sub-carrier assignment, and antenna precoding—based on semantic insights provided by higher-layer intelligence or edge AI models. O-RAN’s disaggregated architecture, particularly the Near-RT RIC, offers a natural control point to enable this adaptive physical-layer orchestration through closed-loop feedback and policy-based control.

L2, encompassing the MAC layer along with its interaction with the Radio Link Control (RLC) and Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) sublayers, is equally critical for semantic communication. At the MAC layer, scheduling decisions must evolve beyond static service categories such as enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) or Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC). Instead, schedulers should prioritize transmissions based on the contextual relevance and urgency of packet content. This can be achieved by embedding semantic metadata or tags within packet headers, enabling the scheduler to make informed, semantics-driven transmission decisions.

¹In this work, we define meaning as the task-relevant interpretation inferred from messages exchanged within a shared context, inspired by the semantic communication model of [16].

Fig. 3. Text vs Image score

In such a semantic framework, it becomes important to ask whether retransmitting a particular segment is actually necessary from a meaning preservation standpoint. This is demonstrated in Fig. 3, which depicts a scatter plot illustrating the relationship between image score (x-axis) and text score (y-axis) for a semantic classification task. Each point corresponds to one sample, and different colors represent different MCS levels (20, 24, and 25). The plot reveals a clear positive correlation between image and text scores, indicated by the dotted diagonal line. Higher MCS values produce more dispersed score distributions, while lower MCS values lead to tighter clusters with higher scores, suggesting improved semantic performance under robust modulation and coding schemes in a wireless channel without retransmission.

IV. CASE STUDY I – MAC PROTOCOL DESIGN FOR PUSH-PULL DATA TRANSMISSION

The architectural components introduced in Sections II and III realize a coherent and hierarchical semantic control plane, enabling semantic communications to be not only algorithmically effective, but also architecturally grounded, scalable, and deployable within future 6G networks. The first case study illustrates how the proposed RIC-centric semantic framework is instantiated at the Near-RT control level, focusing on semantic-aware MAC adaptation for data collection in IoT scenarios. Within the proposed architecture of Fig. 1, this use case activates the semantic management loop and adaptive L1/L2 control, translating semantic relevance and application-driven priorities into MAC-level scheduling and access decisions. The case study shows how fast time-scale semantic control can be enforced at the RAN edge, while remaining coordinated with higher-level orchestration policies.

A central challenge in the development of 6G networks is deciding *when* and *how* to collect data efficiently for edge and cloud processing [17]. This challenge is acute in IoT scenarios, where a limited subset of nodes within a large sensor population may provide relevant information for

downstream applications. Efficient and timely data collection, therefore, relies on VoI-driven retrieval strategies. VoI is often estimated using models such as Digital Twins (DTs), which rely on statistical assumptions and may not accurately reflect the true VoI distribution. As a result, data collection must account for model uncertainty and cases where VoI cannot be evaluated before transmission. These constraints motivate a hybrid data-collection paradigm that integrates push- and pull-based communication, allowing sensor-initiated transmissions to coexist with Base Station (BS)-coordinated retrieval.

In IoT systems, *pull-based communication* enables the BS to retrieve data from selected nodes through queries. By dynamically configuring the query content, the BS can control which nodes transmit based on data relevance or semantics, thereby reducing traffic and energy consumption. In contrast, *push-based communication* allows nodes to transmit as soon as data become available, prioritizing timeliness. Push traffic relies on random access, whereas pull traffic uses scheduled transmissions under BS coordination. This fundamental difference complicates the development of MAC protocols for efficient traffic coexistence. Time-division MAC schemes addressing this challenge have been proposed in [17], [18].

One such MAC design for push-pull coexistence [18], illustrated at the top of Fig. 4, divides each frame into two sub-frames: (i) **scheduled contention-free slots** for pull traffic, and (ii) **random access contention-based slots** for push traffic. The resource split is controlled by $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. Specifically, of the total of S time slots, $\lfloor \alpha S \rfloor$ are allocated to pull devices, and the remainder to push devices. A control signal preceding the contention-free slots enables the BS to retrieve data from high-VoI devices without packet collisions. This design supports coexistence without mutual interference, and allows the BS to adapt the push-pull resource split by tuning α according to the application status, sensor availability, and supported access modes. Building on this structure, we propose a RIC-centric orchestration of data collection, enabling adaptive control of MAC parameters in response to application dynamics.

To illustrate this approach, consider an O-RAN deployment in which IoT UE data are collected through the RAN to update a DT model deployed at an edge server. To track time-varying application and UE states, an xApp at the Near-RT RIC orchestrates interactions between the DT and IoT sensors. The xApp interprets application requirements to generate UE access policies, translating DT demands—such as preferred type of content and latency constraints—into push-pull resource allocation and pull-query configuration. The xApp also processes and forwards received IoT data, ensuring that only information that improves DT updates is delivered, thereby reducing unnecessary data traffic. The evaluation in the bottom of Fig. 4 shows how optimal-latency resource split depends on traffic characteristics. In Scenario 1, a minimum latency of 20 ms is achieved with an 80%-20% push-pull resource split, reflecting the higher push traffic. In Scenario 2, the same latency is achieved with a 20%-80% split, driven by the higher pull traffic. Latency is minimized when slot allocation matches traffic rates, balancing the probability of pull-query satisfaction

Fig. 4. Time-division frame design for push-pull traffic coexistence (top) and achievable latency at 99% reliability as a function of the resource allocation for pull traffic (bottom). Each scenario is characterized by the average pull and push arrival rates, denoted by $\lambda = (\lambda_{\text{pull}}, \lambda_{\text{push}})$ in units of 10^3 packets/s. The simulation setup follows [17].

and push-traffic packet collision [18].

Overall, this case study demonstrates how semantic relevance and application-level objectives can be effectively translated into fast time-scale MAC adaptations via the Near-RT RIC. By dynamically orchestrating push-pull resource allocation based on DT-driven data requirements, the proposed RIC-centric framework enables latency-efficient and resource-aware IoT data collection at the RAN edge. These results confirm the feasibility of semantic control loops operating close to L1/L2, while remaining aligned with higher-level orchestration policies envisioned for 6G networks.

V. CASE STUDY II – SEMANTIC-AWARE COLLABORATIVE INFERENCE AT THE EDGE

This case study focuses on semantic-aware edge intelligence and illustrates how semantic processing and collaborative inference can be orchestrated across devices and edge resources within the proposed framework. From an architectural perspective (see Figs. 1, 2), it primarily engages the Non-RT RIC semantic orchestration functions, which operate over longer time scales to coordinate model placement, inference strategies, and collaboration policies, while interacting with Near-RT mechanisms for execution. The use case highlights how semantic relevance and channel awareness jointly drive decisions on where and how inference is performed, bridging AI model behavior with network-level constraints.

More in depth, one of the objectives of AI-native wireless networks is to interconnect intelligent agents that share collected information to (collaboratively) solve complex tasks. These agents will perform more or less complex operations, with models that are heterogeneous in terms of computational burden, training, and task specialization among others. Then, multiple problems arise, including smart choices on if and where to offload workloads, and most importantly how to

represent information based on this choice or vice versa, or ultimately how to jointly optimize data representation, computing-related choices for AI workloads, and radio resources. Although current networks are agnostic of the content or purpose of the bits they reliably transport, a promising direction is to determine how application and semantic-awareness can help exploring new optimization opportunities [19].

Edge inference can take place in different ways: (i) **on-device inference**, typically with models running on resource-poor hardware; (ii) **edge computing**, in proximal edge servers on raw data received by end devices; (iii) **vertical collaboration**, with end devices extracting relevant information (semantics) for the purpose of the task (e.g., classification, object detection), thus reducing communication load at the cost of local computation; (iv) **horizontal collaboration**, with end devices sharing raw data or relevant information among each other to improve local performance. Each of these come with different opportunities and challenges/threats: (i) does not require communication and improve privacy, but requires embedding AI models locally and increasing hardware deployment; (ii) offloads computational burden to nearby servers that can handle multiple tasks, but increases communication overhead, especially in uplink; (iii) introduces a higher level of flexibility, but inherently an additional layer of decision making (e.g., what and how to offload?); (iv) reduces the involvement of the network, but requires coordination among devices. Here, we focus on (iv) with the concept of semantic and channel-aware device grouping for collaborative inference.

When devices collect data from real environments, the latter could be corrupted or incomplete, thus leading to poor inference performance when computation takes place locally. Collaborating with neighbor devices that collect possibly correlated data can help improving performance. However, who should a device collaborate with? At least two aspects are fundamental: the wireless channel quality to reach other devices, and the relevance of the information they locally possess, with respect to the task at hand. How to discover the relevance of other devices' information is at the core of the collaboration grouping. In fact, directly sharing data could be intractable due to the communication burden. However, in [20], the authors show how only a very low-dimensional representation is enough to group devices into collaborating clusters, to then share the actual information (or, a semantic representation) to be aggregated and take the final decision (e.g., classification, object detection). This sharing is only performed within each cluster, thus reducing the communication costs. These clusters are formed on the basis of a matching score that depends on the mutual relevance of local data.

In [11], it is argued how the information relevance (semantics) and channel quality should be taken into account to maximize the effectiveness of horizontal collaboration. To design a joint approach, the Key-Query mechanism exploited in [20] is extended to a channel-aware matching score calculation. This makes the cluster formation more robust to two potentially detrimental situations: (1) a very high relevance of data, but a very bad channel condition, and (2) a very good channel

Fig. 5. Comparison of the different collaborative inference methods in terms of accuracy for different query sizes. Dataset: CIFAR-100. Model: MobileNet-v3.

condition, but irrelevant data for the local purpose.

The benefits of the joint channel and semantic-aware approach are illustrated in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5, different methods are compared in a scenario where devices have partial observation and sharing their observations may be subjected to an additive white Gaussian noise channel, for different query sizes. The compared baselines include a semantic-aware only approach; local observation only; full observation, which serves as an upper performance limit; and semantic-aware without any channel impairments, denoted as perfect communication. The robustness of the joint approach can be noted by the superior performance even for low query sizes, approaching the performance of perfect communication, suggesting that the joint approach is able to effectively balances data relevance against the channel conditions, enhancing collaboration.

VI. CASE STUDY III – AI-DRIVEN RAN CONTROL IN O-RAN

This case study provides an end-to-end validation of the architectural and operational concepts introduced in Sections II and III, with a strong emphasis on deployment realism and sustainability. We demonstrate the practical realization of the proposed semantic framework through AI-driven rApps deployed within the O-RAN Non-RT RIC over a commercial-grade network. By leveraging AI/ML-driven techniques, the proposed rApps are capable of automating policy management and optimizing network performance, such as energy consumption, inter-cell interference management, and stability maintenance.

In Fig. 6 we showcase the implementation of AI-driven rApps over commercial-grade network scenarios, proving their efficacy in live operational settings. As shown in Fig. 6, the system architecture of rApps with O-RAN networks is presented, which consists of 2 Remote Radio Units (RRUs), Front-Haul Gateways (FHGWs), BaseBand Units (BBUs), and 5G Core. A suite of rApps—i.e., Key Performance Measurement (KPM) rApp and Energy Saving (ES) rApps—could be developed and maintained at Non-RT RIC located with SMO

Fig. 6. System architecture of rApps with O-RAN network.

framework to achieve policy management and system reconfigurations. The ES-rApp functions as an AI-native, closed-loop control system within the Non-RT RIC framework to dynamically optimize energy efficiency in live 5G environments.

The workflow begins with the collection of KPMs, including resource block utilization, throughput, and real-time power metrics from physical layer components like BBUs and RRUs via the O1 interface. These metrics are validated and stored in an InfluxDB database, where they are subsequently processed by the KPM-rApp to filter anomalies and generate enriched traffic and power profiles. The ES-rApp then utilizes these features to fuel Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based prediction models that forecast short-term traffic load variations, allowing the Resource Management Engine to formulate proactive energy-saving strategies such as deactivating under-utilized cells or adjusting transmit power. These strategies are validated against service-level policies before being enforced via the O1 interface or shared with the Near-RT RIC via the A1 interface for near-real-time execution. Finally, the system maintains a continuous feedback loop by monitoring updated KPMs to reassess performance and trigger rollbacks if QoS degradation occurs, so as to achieve improved energy efficiency without compromising network reliability. As shown in Fig. 7, with the live power traces, this rApp based power control allows the system to drop total power consumption from a baseline of approximately 54W to roughly 37.5W during low-load intervals while maintaining strict quality of service requirements.

Overall, this case study demonstrates the practical feasibility of AI-driven rApps for semantic control, which offers a foundation for advancing operational efficiency, environmental sustainability, and cross-domain orchestration in goal-oriented mobile networks. By integrating predictive intelli-

Fig. 7. Empirical energy consumption evaluation for the developed ES-rApp over O-RAN networks.

gence with closed-loop automation within the O-RAN Non-RT RIC framework, AI-driven RAN control has the potential to improve the operation efficiency over practical networks.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper addressed the challenge of realizing semantic communications in practical 6G systems by showing how semantic methodologies can be effectively integrated with network control and operation across heterogeneous time scales. Through three complementary case studies, we demonstrated how semantic-aware solutions can be instantiated across different layers, reducing communication overhead and enabling flexible operation in realistic deployments. Specific attention was also devoted to sustainability and energy-related aspects, considering the energy footprint of the system as a whole rather than focusing solely on run-time communication gains. The resulting evaluation aimed to provide insights and to emphasize the importance of holistic, architecture-aware energy assessment in semantic communications. The results indicate that the effectiveness and impact of semantic communications critically depend on their functional integration with network operations, providing practical guidance toward deployable, AI-native 6G systems.

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